

Social Lyrics in the Creation of Xurshid Davron

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the poet's poem "Trust". The changes in the politics of the period, the hardships that befell the people, and the actions of the ruling ideology in the policy of cotton slavery are critically evaluated.*

Key words: *Telman Gdlyan, cotton work, citizen lyric, era and human issue.*

When we think about the literature of the 20th century, we see examples of ideologized works written within certain patterns. But it should not be forgotten that precisely this stagnation, literature subordinated to ideological politics, left the framework of our classical literature in the traditional form and led to genres, different forms and styles of world literature.

"Let's also remember that the new Uzbek literature was mainly formed under the influence of 19th-century European, as well as modern Indian, Arabic, and Turkish literature experiences, for example, R. Tagor Cholpon, J. Zaydon Qadiri served as a role model and mentor. . However, in the 1920s and 1930s, creative research went at a very fast pace; our writers, in Qadiri's words, tried to attract the interest of our people to new things as much as possible, to introduce the "latest trends" in modern world literature... Especially, Cholpon's prose and Oybek's lyrics are exemplary in this regard. Unfortunately, such principles did not reach the level of sustainable creative flow. The socio-political environment and literary policy of the Soviet era did not allow this." (1; 23-24)

The politics of the period shaped a narrow class outlook. Censorship was established over the freedom of speech, which is as necessary for the artist as water and air. As a result, even the most intelligent stratum of the nation was forced to compromise with politics, those who did not do so were cruelly punished, exiled to the forests of Siberia, shot to death as "nationalists", and their family members were deprived of the most basic human rights and needs. , their children were branded as "Child of the Enemy of the People", "Kashqirvachcha born from Kashkir". They were not accepted into the party until they renounced their family members, who were considered enemies of the people. This was the worst disaster for a Soviet man. In the poetry of this period, the images of happy growers, happy children, master farmers with full threshing floors of the Soviet countries were in the center of attention. Humans have been reduced to robots who only follow orders. The events of the period are expressed with great pathos in prose works such as Togay Murad's "Fields left by my father", "Iron Woman" by Sharaf Boshbekov, "Ikki karra two - five" by Otkir Hashimov. along with Xurshid Davron's works, he also mentions them. The poet's poem "Trust" is important because it illuminates the scenes of cotton slavery, the main idea of the above-mentioned prose works. The important thing is that the poet is not afraid of anything, the landscape is embodied in the eyes of the reader, like a picture drawn by an artist or film strips.

Forty-four million, Comrade Gdlyan,

Do you want us to return it to the Uzbek boy?

Now he stole his name

You have eaten the sorrow of my motherland (2:160)

The poem begins with an unusual tone of irony. As a result of Telman Gdlyan's investigation on the "Cotton Case" in Uzbekistan in 1983-1989, thousands of Uzbek cotton farmers lost their lives. Anyone involved in or associated with cotton growing was viewed with suspicion. Finally, in 1989, a criminal case was opened against Gdlyan and his accomplice Ivanov, but these cases were dropped due to political changes in 1990. The poet reveals his hatred towards those who, instead of coming to investigate and verifying the real situation and establishing justice, created panic in people's hearts and deprived them of their trust, hope and life. Failure to take care of them reminds them that it is their duty to return the money. The poet is surprised that this money can fill the pockets of our people, who have never seen so much money even in their dreams, but who are accused of offering bribes to the center, but still have a small part of their heart. The poet himself gives an explanation for such a confused state. Just as a broken cup does not return to its original state after a thousand strokes, human dignity has been trampled once, no matter how hard you try to justify your name, it will not be the same as before.

Oh, the people whose cup of patience is full

If he moves, the mountains will be low in front of him,

His hands are full,

Lashes dagger,

The example of Alpomish will be great.

These verses are similar in form and content to the poem "Khalk" by Cholpon, a shining star of modern poetry. It is necessary to return this money to the people, but what kind of power and prayer can bring back the sufferings of the people, their life deprived of feelings and dreams. The poet is confused about such things that cannot be reversed. The breed of poets understands our unseen and sometimes ignored pains better than we do, analyzes them more deeply and tries to hold a mirror to our faces.

"The creators of the next period tried to use more effective, effective and truthful methods of expression. Including, the transfer of the elements characteristic of the art of painting to poetry, made it possible to present the visual expression in it as if the artist had drawn it. Of course, in this case, the picture drawn with the help of words, not colors, is embodied in the imagination thanks to the artist's skill."(3;41) "Young children who lost their morning sleep", "Young girls bent like old women", "Brides like flowers who died without giving birth", red Who will bring back the lost lives of women who burned themselves and became "living flags" without shelter from slogans?

When to these hearts

Joy returns,

Who gives speech to dumb hearts?

Tell me your pain, my people,

open your heart

Otherwise, it will make your heart sad.

Xurshid Davron is well aware that trust is the power that saves the people in this situation. He emphasizes that awakening the hunger for truth in hearts is the most important factor in the unification of the nation. If the love of the Motherland and the people takes over the hearts, he emphasizes that the money Gdlyan wants to bring to the Uzbek people will turn into a pittance.

The work of the poet is notable for the fact that in each of his poems, the problems of the era and the people are placed crosswise. In general, the concept of time is an abstract concept. It is constantly changing depending on social reality. "It can be said that the poet, while subtly following the leading trends of the time, can embody them in the ideological and aesthetic content of his poems. that is, only if he can reflect the typical experiences and feelings that are close and dear to the people, the

reader will accept the poet "me" as his "me" and see himself in this "me". 4;11) These characteristics ensure the survival of Xurshid Davron's work.

The concept of "citizen's lyric" is often found in the poetry of this period. At the core of this concept lies creativity that cares about the life, present and future of its people, realizes that it is not enough to sing about people's pain, and is on the way to find concrete solutions to problems. Xurshid Davron is considered to be an active participant of social lyrics because of his poems that make the reader think and think, such as "Trust", "Kuzni Oyla", "Poem about an old woman", "Alfalfa reaping" can take.

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